

1 *Girdling in litchi*

2 **Flower induction through girdling: A way to minimize alternate bearing in**
3 **litchi cv. China**

4 **M.K. Dhakar, Bikash Das*, Sridhar Gutam**, Prakash Patil** and A.K. Singh**

5 Farming System Research Centre for Hill and Plateau Region, ICAR–Research Complex for
6 Eastern Region, Patna – 800014, Bihar, India

7 **ABSTRACT**

8 **In litchi, certain cultivars are prone to alternate bearing. To counteract the alternate**
9 **bearing, an experiment was conducted on annual guided branch girdling for four**
10 **consecutive fruit bearing years using a commercial plantation of litchi cv. China litchi at**
11 **Ranchi, India. Trees were girdled by removing a bark strip (2, 4 and 6 mm width) circularly**
12 **around the selected 25% and 50% primary branches. During OFF- years, the flowering was**
13 **increased by 8.62 (2017) and 4.37 (2019) times whereas; it was 3.49 (2015) and 1.68 (2018)**
14 **times higher during ON-years with the L2G2 treatment (4 mm width girdling of 50%**
15 **primary branches). Treatment L2G2 also showed the highest cumulative yield with 201.19**
16 **kg/tree from four years, while the control showed the lowest cumulative yield with 96.98**
17 **kg/tree. After four years, the pooled fruit yield data showed that the highest average yield**
18 **was recorded in L2G2 treatment (50.30 kg/ tree), and it was found to be the lowest in the**
19 **control (24.24 kg/ tree). The pooled data also showed that the highest average alternate**
20 **bearing index (*I*) value (0.73) was observed in the control treatment whereas it was the lowest**

*Corresponding Author's Email: bikash41271@gmail.com

**Project Coordinator Cell (Fruits), ICAR – Indian Institute of Horticultural Research, Hessaraghatta Lake Post, Bengaluru560 089, Karnataka, India

21 (0.32) in L2G1 (2 mm width girdling of 50% primary branches) followed by L2G2 (0.35)
22 treatment. The Long-Term Yield Index (LTYI) ranged from 31.01% in control to 122.25%
23 in L2G2 treatment. Therefore, 4 mm width girdling of 50% primary branches, reduces
24 alternate bearing behaviour of litchi cv. China. In our experiment, cumulative yield was
25 increased by 2.07 times (under L2G2) as compared to un-girdled trees during the four years
26 of the trial.

27 **Keywords:** *Litchi chinensis* Sonn., alternate bearing, yield, girdling, long-term yield index,

28 INTRODUCTION

29 The yield of many fruit trees is erratic due to the occurrence of varying degrees of alternate
30 and irregular bearings occurring at varying degrees. Alternate bearing has an impact on a few fruit
31 trees that consists of the changes in the yield level with a high yield ("ON" year) and a low yield
32 ("OFF" year) in the following year. This pattern repeats year after year. There are several reports
33 about alternate bearing in fruit plants, including pistachio, pecan, olive, and apple. Apart from
34 these, avocado, citrus, peach, litchi, mango, hazelnut and chestnut are also prone to alternate
35 bearing (Monselise and Goldschmidt, 12). Alternate bearing results from genetic characteristics,
36 growth conditions, endogenous hormonal level, crop load and impact of other particular annual
37 variables related to carbohydrate storage and mobilization (Barnett and Mielke, 3; Wood, 18). The
38 area under litchi in India is approximately 95000 hectares and produces 727000 tonnes of fruit
39 every year (Anonymous, 1). Litchi has a narrow genetic base in India (Bajpai *et al.*, 2) and the
40 number of commercial cultivars is limited to only 8-10. In fruit crops, alternate bearing also differs
41 with varieties. Litchi cv. 'China' has a strong tendency to alternate but is an above-average yielder
42 with shorter canopy, less prone to cracking and consistently good quality fruits during the "ON"
43 year. These attributes could probably be a reason for its use in commercial plantings in India. The

44 intra plant variation in flushing and shoot growth pattern was also found to influence the overall
45 floriferousness of the litchi plants as suggested by Das *et al.* (5). In contrast with many litchi
46 varieties, ‘China’ variety matures late in the growing season, leaving little time for carbohydrate
47 storage to support the growing flowers and fruit of the next season Malhotra *et al.*(11). This trait,
48 when combined with a heavy fruit set, would leave ‘China’ trees with depleted carbohydrate
49 reserves at the end of the season and lead to poor fruit set in the following year. A useful method
50 for the quantification of alternate bearing is through the measurement of the alternate bearing index
51 (ABI), which is expressed as I (Pearce and Doberšek-Urbanc, 14). Across a diverse range of fruit
52 species and cultivars, I ranged on a scale of 0 to 1 (0 = no alternate bearing; 1 = total alternate
53 bearing). The alternate bearing of this magnitude disrupts marketing by precipitating strong
54 fluctuations in net return to the growers and processors.

55 Despite advances in horticultural techniques, alternative bearings remain a key constrain
56 in the production of fruit crops. Improved horticultural practices have decreased the severity of
57 alternate bearing in many fruit crops. The most effective strategies for reducing alternation are
58 through raising the amount of carbohydrate available for the next season, fruit thinning, branch
59 girdling, and increasing exposure to sunlight by pruning and ensuring sufficient supply of soil,
60 water and nutrients (Conner and Worley, 4). Girdling, appeared to be the best option for controlling
61 the alternate bearing of litchi (Li and Xiao, 10). In this technique, a portion of bark (phloem) is
62 removed from the wood by using a girdling knife. Since the woody xylem part remains intact,
63 water and nutrient reaches the leaves. When photosynthates are prepared, they are not transported
64 to other sections below the girdle and photosynthates are accumulated just above the girdle region
65 that increases the C:N ratio and support the flowering (Kumar *et al.*, 8). Girdling has a positive
66 impact on the plant by encouraging regular bearing, larger fruit size and quality enhancement.

67 However, if girdling is done incorrectly, the plant will die due to root starvation. Girdling has the
68 drawback of inhibiting assimilate transfer to the roots. Litchi is an important woody mycorrhizal
69 fruit tree. However, girdling adversely affects carbohydrate transport from shoot to the root, which
70 restricts litchi's mycorrhizal root development and root absorption (Shu *et al.*, 16). As a
71 consequence, the girdling of all primary shoots in litchi can affect plant health. Hence, now-a-days
72 it is not advisable to girdle all primary branches. Recently Kumar *et al.* (8) also conducted girdling
73 on 25 per cent and 50 per cent of the primary branches in cv. 'Shahi', and Sruamsiri *et al.* (17)
74 indicated that the girdling of 50 per cent of the branches favoured a more frequent flowering in
75 litchi. There is inadequate information on how this girdling affects the alternate bearing index, the
76 alternate bearing intensity and the long-term yield index (LTYI) in cv. 'China'. Therefore, the
77 prime objective of this work was to test the effect of different girdling treatments on flowering,
78 fruiting, quality and alternate bearing parameters in litchi cv. 'China'.

79 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

80 Experimental litchi orchard located near Ranchi city, Jharkhand, India (23°16' N latitude,
81 85° 50' E longitude) at an altitude of 651m. The field was located entirely within a single soil type,
82 sandy-loam, with a pH range of 4.5-5.5. The region represents a hot-dry, sub-humid climate. The
83 long-term maximum average temperature was 29.5°C and the long-term average minimum
84 temperature was 18.0°C. Rainfall shows an annual average of 1,316 mm.

85 The orchard reached peak production prior to the start of the experiment and data collection
86 began when trees were 32 years old. There was apparent hailstorm during October 2015 which
87 resulted in no flowering during January 2016. Although 2017 was expected to be an ON year of
88 fruiting, the flower intensity recorded during the year indicated an OFF year. Looking at the
89 intensity of damage to the plants by the hailstorm during October, 2015, the low flower intensity

90 during 2017 can be attributed to the inability of the trees to recoup out of the stress induced by the
 91 hailstorm even after one year. The lower assimilate content in the plant during 2016 as a result of
 92 heavy fruiting in 2015 combined with complete defoliation of the plants for a prolonged duration
 93 during 2016 due to hailstorm leading to poor accumulation of assimilates might have contributed
 94 towards the low flowering intensity during 2017. The study was conducted during the production
 95 cycles of 2015 (ON year), 2017 (OFF year), 2018 (ON year) and 2019 (OFF year) in 32-year-old
 96 ‘China’ variety planted in square system at spacing of 10 m x 10 m (100 trees ha⁻¹). Plants were
 97 maintained under the rainfed conditions and with pruning of litchi terminal branches at 40 cm after
 98 harvesting (2nd week of June). Girdling treatment was applied to 25% (L1) and 50% (L2) primary
 99 branches by removing 2 mm (G1), 4 mm (G2) and 6 mm (G3) width bark. Litchi trees with four
 100 primary branches were chosen for the study to maintain uniformity, and the girdling was done 10
 101 cm above the origin of the primary branches.

Plate 1. The photographs showing different girdling treatment on primary branches.

A. 2 mm width girdling B. 4 mm width girdling C. 6 mm with girdling.

102

103 Sufficient care was taken to select the branches with uniform diameter for imposing the girdling
 104 treatments. The diameter of all the primary branches under the study ranged from 75 to 80 cm. In order to
 105 impose a 25% and 50% girdling treatment on a tree, one and two primary branch was girdled,
 106 respectively. A treatment without any girdling served as control (LOG0). Thus, the experiment
 107 consisted of seven treatments such as L1G1 (Girdling of 25% primary branches + 2 mm girdling),
 108 L1G2 (Girdling of 25% primary branches + 4 mm girdling), L1G3 (Girdling of 25% primary
 109 branches + 6 mm girdling), L2G1 (Girdling of 50% primary branches + 2 mm girdling), L2G2
 110 (Girdling of 50% primary branches + 4 mm girdling), L2G3 (Girdling of 50% primary branches +
 111 6 mm girdling) and control (without girdling) arranged in three replications. Each replicate consists
 112 of two trees. The girdling operation performed every year during 1st week of september. A bark
 113 strip (2, 4 and 6 mm width) was removed in a circular fashion around the selected 25% and 50%
 114 primary branches which suppressed carbohydrate and hormonal transfer to the roots. In the first
 115 year, the girdling on the primary branch was performed close to the base and then stepped up to 5
 116 cm each year. Plant protection and cultural practices have been carried out based on guidelines for
 117 litchi orchards with an integrated approach.

118 The observation on per cent flowering shoot was recorded in the month of first week of
 119 March from tagged shoots (50 numbers in first week of November) in each direction prior to
 120 flowering. The final fruit yield of ON and OFF year was calculated for each treatment over four
 121 successive bearing cycles and the data collected was used for the calculation of the alternate
 122 bearing index (ABI). The fluctuation in yield was expressed in terms of the alternate bearing index
 123 (*I*), and calculated as per formula given in Table 1:

124 **Table 1. The details of the formula used in the study.**

S. No.	Parameter	Formula	Details of abbreviations	Reference
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1.	Alternate bearing index (<i>I</i>)	$I = 1 / (n-1) \sqrt{\{ (a_2 - a_1) / (a_2 + a_1) + (a_3 - a_2) / (a_3 + a_2) \dots + (a_n - a_{n-1}) / (a_n + a_{n-1})\}}$	n = number of years, and a ₁ , a ₂ , ..., a _(n-1) , a _n = yields of corresponding years	(Pearce and Doberšek-Urbanc, 14)
2.	Alternate bearing intensity	Alternate bearing intensity = [standard deviation of yield (years analyzed) / average yield (years analyzed)] * 100		Noperi-Mosqueda <i>et al.</i> (13)
3.	Long-term yield index	Long-term yield index = (average yield of the years analyzed / alternate bearing intensity) * 100		Noperi-Mosqueda <i>et al.</i> (13)

125 To calculate the alternate bearing intensity and long-term yield index, the formula reported
126 by Noperi-Mosqueda *et al.* (13) was used:

127 Mean fruit, peel and seed weight were determined using the analytical balance (Mettler
128 Toledo, PB403-S) based on 50 fruit samples taken randomly from each replication. Treatments
129 consisting of girdling, fruit samples were taken from the girdled branches. Aril % was calculated
130 using the formulae: pulp weight/fruit weight × 100. Fruit length and width were measured at the
131 maximum point with a digital vernier caliper (RSK™, 150 mm, 0.01 mm reading capacity). TSS
132 (°Brix) was recorded using a digital refractometer (ATAGO PAL-1, Japan, Range 0-53°Brix) and
133 each sample used to assess the TSS content consisted of 10 randomly selected fruits. Titratable
134 acidity was estimated using 0.1 N sodium hydroxide solution Ranganna, S. (15). Total sugar was
135 determined using a volumetric method based on the principle of reduction of Fehling's solution
136 Lane and Eynon (9).

137 A randomized block design with three replicates and two trees per replication was used.
138 Mean separation was conducted using Duncan's test with a 5 % significance level using SPSS
139 version 20.

140 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

141 Girdling treatments had a significant effect on per cent flowering shoots in litchi cv. China
 142 during ON and OFF-years. The 4 mm width girdling of 50% primary branches (L2G2) had
 143 significantly higher per cent flowering shoots than other treatments during all the four years of
 144 experiment. Treatment L2G2 had 39.72, 29.39, 68.17 and 29.36% flowering shoots during 2015,
 145 2017, 2018 and 2019, respectively (Table 2). During OFF-years the percent increase in flowering
 146 was 725.56% (2017) and 336.90% (2019) whereas; it was 248.73% (2015) and 67.58% (2018)
 147 during ON-years. Li and Xiao (10) stated that the girdling treatment increased the flowering as
 148 compared to the untreated 'Nuomici' litchi trees and this would be an important basis for good
 149 cropping. The additional presence of carbohydrate in leaves and shoots was associated with
 150 increased flowering due to reduced carbohydrate flow to the roots (Xianjun *et al.*, 19).

151 **Table 2.** Effect of girdling on flowering (%) from four subsequent bearing cycles (2015-2019).

Symbol	Treatment	2015	2017	2018	2019
		(ON year)	(OFF year)	(ON year)	(OFF year)
L1G1	25% PB + 2 mm G	27.22±2.72 ^c	6.86±0.90 ^{de}	40.58±2.42 ^{de}	8.31±0.49 ^e
L2G1	50% PB + 2 mm G	25.56±1.64 ^c	22.11±1.55 ^b	46.33±3.08 ^c	23.75±1.58 ^b
L1G2	25% PB + 4 mm G	18.33±2.04 ^d	10.42±2.50 ^c	51.26±2.01 ^b	10.88±0.43 ^d
L2G2	50% PB + 4 mm G	39.72±3.64 ^a	29.39±3.46 ^a	68.17±2.97 ^a	29.36±1.28 ^a
L1G3	25% PB + 6 mm G	32.78±1.83 ^b	10.14±3.84 ^{cd}	40.42±2.52 ^e	10.34±0.65 ^d
L2G3	50% PB + 6 mm G	33.61±2.68 ^b	21.67±4.33 ^b	45.01±2.64 ^{cd}	20.35±1.19 ^c
L0G0	Control	11.39±0.76 ^e	3.56±1.26 ^e	40.68±2.49 ^{de}	6.72±0.41 ^e

In a column, means with the same small superscript letters are not significantly different according to Duncan's test at a significance level of 5%. Results showed Mean±SD. PB: Primary branch, G: Girdling

152 **Table 3.** Effect of girdling on annual fruit yield (kg/tree) from four subsequent bearing cycles
 153 (2015-2019).

Symbol	Treatments	2015	2017	2018	2019
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		(ON year)	(OFF year)	(ON year)	(OFF year)
L1G1	25% PB + 2 mm G	45.52±6.58 ^{bc}	7.89±2.17 ^d	43.67±2.60 ^c	15.40±2.93 ^d
L2G1	50% PB + 2 mm G	48.74±6.54 ^{bc}	25.43±2.21 ^b	46.29±3.08 ^c	22.31±1.94 ^c
L1G2	25% PB + 4 mm G	52.46±4.10 ^b	11.98±1.64 ^c	55.94±2.19 ^b	17.51±2.40 ^d
L2G2	50% PB + 4 mm G	65.23±9.61 ^a	33.80±2.87 ^a	70.40±3.06 ^a	31.77±4.52 ^a
L1G3	25% PB + 6 mm G	40.82±7.21 ^c	11.66±0.89 ^{cd}	44.98±2.81 ^c	16.89±4.37 ^d
L2G3	50% PB + 6 mm G	53.53±8.16 ^b	24.92±3.03 ^b	58.76±3.45 ^b	25.40±2.25 ^b
L0G0	Control	38.35±2.59 ^c	4.09±0.51 ^e	42.27±2.59 ^c	12.27±1.55 ^e

In a column, means with the same small superscript letters are not significantly different according to Duncan's test at a significance level of 5%. Results showed Mean±SD. PB: Primary branch, G: Girdling

154 Litchi fruit yield among ON and OFF-years and within years varied with different girdling
155 treatments. Mean yields in the two ON producing years (2015 and 2018) were greater than mean
156 yields in the two OFF producing years (2017 and 2019). Severe reduction in yield from the ON to
157 the OFF years indicates a deficit in tree's carbohydrate reserves during the OFF year because of
158 heavy fruiting during the ON year. Furthermore increase in yield in the subsequent ON year
159 indicated sufficient reserves of carbohydrate in the OFF year because of low production of yield
160 the same year. Four mm wide girdling in 50 per cent primary branches (L2G2) on annual yield per
161 tree have shown that girdling mitigated alternate bearing (Table 3). Trees that had received L2G2
162 treatment had higher yields to control trees over the course of the four years. Under L2G2
163 treatment, a full four-year yield assessment showed the highest yield in the 2015 and 2018 (65.23
164 and 70.4 kg/tree, respectively) and the lowest in the 2017 and 2019 (33.80 and 31.77 kg/tree,
165 respectively). The comparison between the best treatment (L2G2) and control showed that the
166 highest increase in yields was observed during the OFF-year period, *i.e.* in the 2017 (726.41%)
167 and 2019 (158.92%) and the lowest increase in yields in ON-years, *i.e.* in 2015(70.09%) and 2018
168 (66.55%). The girdling showed a direct impact because the accumulation of carbohydrate related
169 to the yield of litchi (Xianjun *et al.*, 19). Thus, the girdling of 50% primary branches with 4 mm

170 width allows rising accumulation of carbohydrate in branches without diminishing yield. This
 171 could be due to the fact that girdling facilitates the assimilation carbohydrate and growth
 172 regulators. Therefore, in our study, girdling (50% primary branches with 4 mm width) is probably
 173 positive to increase the bearing and yield. Huang *et al.* (6) also found that the effect of girdling on
 174 the fruit yield of young litchi cultivars ‘Nuomici’ and ‘Guiwei’ was significant. The L2G2
 175 treatment also showed the highest cumulative yield with 201.19 kg/tree from four years, while the
 176 control showed the lowest cumulative yield with 96.98 kg/tree. The pooled fruit yield data of four
 177 years showed that the highest average yield was recorded in L2G2 treatment (50.30 kg/ tree), and
 178 the lowest in control (24.24 kg/ tree) (Fig. 1).

179

180 **Fig. 1.** Cumulative yield per tree in kg/plant (A), pooled yield in kg/plant (B), alternate bearing
 181 intensity (%) (C) and long term yield index (%) (D) of litchi var. ‘China’. T1 (L1G1), T2 (L2G1),
 182 T3 (L1G2), T4 (L2G2), T5 (L1G3) and T6 (L2G3).

183 The *I* value under various girdling treatments was evaluated between ON- and OFF-year
184 yields. The *I* value decreased from 0.81 under control to 0.31 and 0.32 ($p < 0.05$) under treatment
185 L2G1 and L2G2, respectively when compared first ON-year and second OFF-year yields,
186 respectively. This pattern has been consistent in year-on-year yields from the second OFF to the
187 third ON-year and yields from the third ON-year to the fourth OFF-year. The pooled data showed
188 that the highest average *I* value was observed in the control treatment (0.73) and the lowest in
189 L2G1 (0.32) followed by L2G2 (0.35) treatment (Table 4). All girdling treatments reduced the
190 severity of the alternate bearing in litchi cv. China. From 2015 through 2019, girdled trees had
191 more annual yield than control (un-girdled). Because of these differences in annual yields, the
192 alternate-bearing index also differed among treatments ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, if the alternate
193 bearing index would be close to 1, differences in crop production between 2 years are very high.
194 The treatment L2G2 (50% PB + 4 mm G) and L2G1 (50% PB + 2 mm G) had *I* values of only
195 0.35 and 0.32, respectively. The yield wise treatment L2G2 gave higher yield than L2G1 but L2G1
196 had lower *I* value due to less fluctuation in yield. Thus using *I* to quantify the extent to which a
197 tree alternate bears can be misleading because this statistic is biased. The alternate bearing index
198 (*I*) is sensitive to the tree's total fruit production (Huff, 7). To address this issue, Noperi-Mosqueda
199 *et al.* (13) proposed two more parameters *i.e.* alternate bearing intensity and long-term yield index.
200 In this study, the average alternative bearings intensity ranged from 78.36% in control trees to
201 39.40% in L2G1 (T2) treatment (Fig. 1). In this study, the average of alternate bearing intensity
202 was lower in L2G1, L2G2 and L2G3 than control. The Long-Term Yield Index (LTYI) has also
203 been determined, which was significantly influenced by various girdling treatments. In the present
204 study, the LTYI ranged from 31.01% in control to 122.25% in L2G2 (T4) treatment (Fig. 1). LTYI
205 is defined as the increasing percentage in productivity over time. It is important to highlight that

206 girdling also has influenced both the production and the alternate bearing intensity, which are
 207 directly related to the LTYI.

208 **Table 4.** Effect of girdling on alternate bearing index (ABI).

Symbol	Treatment	2015-17	2017-18	2018-19	Pooled (2015-19)
L1G1	25% PB + 2 mm G	0.70±0.09 ^{ab}	0.69±0.08 ^b	0.48±0.09 ^b	0.62 ^b
L2G1	50% PB + 2 mm G	0.31±0.03 ^d	0.29±0.07 ^e	0.35±0.07 ^d	0.32 ^d
L1G2	25% PB + 4 mm G	0.63±0.05 ^{bc}	0.65±0.04 ^{bc}	0.52±0.05 ^{ab}	0.60 ^{bc}
L2G2	50% PB + 4 mm G	0.32±0.04 ^d	0.35±0.05 ^{de}	0.38±0.04 ^d	0.35 ^d
L1G3	25% PB + 6 mm G	0.57±0.05 ^c	0.60±0.04 ^c	0.46±0.12 ^{bc}	0.53 ^c
L2G3	50% PB + 6 mm G	0.37±0.11 ^d	0.41±0.08 ^d	0.40±0.01 ^{cd}	0.39 ^d
L0G0	Control	0.81±0.02 ^a	0.82±0.02 ^a	0.55±0.04 ^a	0.73 ^a

In a column, means with the same small superscript letters are not significantly different according to Duncan's test at a significance level of 5%. Results showed Mean±SD. PB: Primary branch, G: Girdling

209 The result of various girdling treatments revealed that T₅ (25 per cent PB + 6 mm G) had
 210 the maximum pooled fruit weight (19.74 g). Among L2G1, L1G2, L2G2 and control treatment,
 211 there was no significant difference in fruit weight. Huang *et al.* (6) also observed that there was no
 212 significant difference in average fruit weight between spiral girdled and control plants of Guiwei
 213 litchi variety. The treatment L1G3 also exhibited the highest pooled fruit volume (18.52cc) during
 214 the study period (2015-2019). There was no significant difference between various treatments for
 215 pooled fruit length. The pooled fruit width in L2G3 treatment was significantly higher (32.02 mm)
 216 than other treatments but did not differ significantly with L1G3 (Table 5). The various girdling
 217 treatments demonstrated no significant difference with control over the aril percentage, acidity (%)
 218 and sugar (%) within four years of study. Only TSS varied due to different girdling treatments and
 219 in treatment T₅ it was maximum (20.31 °Brix) followed by treatments L2G1 and L1G2. There was
 220 no significant difference in TSS between L1G1, L2G2 and the control treatment (Table 6).

221 **Table 5.** Effect of girdling on fruit characteristics (2015-2019).

Symbol	Treatment	Fruit weight (g)	Fruit volume (cc)	Fruit length (mm)	Fruit width (mm)
L1G1	25% PB + 2 mm G	19.24±0.15 ^a	18.11±0.32 ^{abc}	36.83±0.21 ^a	31.45±0.20 ^{bcd}
L2G1	50% PB + 2 mm G	18.30±0.46 ^b	17.11±0.68 ^d	36.25±0.07 ^a	31.51±0.38 ^{bc}
L1G2	25% PB + 4 mm G	18.54±0.40 ^b	17.37±0.32 ^{cd}	36.30±0.51 ^a	31.33±0.08 ^{bcd}
L2G2	50% PB + 4 mm G	18.29±0.47 ^b	17.23±0.48 ^d	36.98±0.77 ^a	31.12±0.44 ^{cd}
L1G3	25% PB + 6 mm G	19.74±0.41 ^a	18.52±0.46 ^a	37.31±0.85 ^a	31.71±0.44 ^{ab}
L2G3	50% PB + 6 mm G	19.73±0.37 ^a	18.31±0.31 ^{ab}	36.74±0.52 ^a	32.02±0.51 ^a
L0G0	Control	18.54±0.65 ^b	17.60±0.59 ^{bcd}	37.60±1.13 ^a	31.02±0.34 ^d

In a column, means with the same small superscript letters are not significantly different according to Duncan's test at a significance level of 5%. Results showed Mean±SD. PB: Primary branch, G: Girdling

222 **Table 6.** Effect of girdling on fruit quality characteristics (2015-2019).

Symbol	Treatment	Aril (%)	TSS (°Brix)	Acidity (%)	Sugar (%)
L1G1	25% PB + 2 mm G	64.15±0.49 ^a	19.21±0.18 ^c	0.25±0.01 ^a	13.00±0.53 ^a
L2G1	50% PB + 2 mm G	63.80±2.11 ^a	20.03±0.40 ^{ab}	0.24±0.01 ^a	13.21±0.23 ^a
L1G2	25% PB + 4 mm G	65.64±2.46 ^a	19.64±0.45 ^{abc}	0.25±0.01 ^a	12.83±0.38 ^a
L2G2	50% PB + 4 mm G	64.51±0.37 ^a	19.05±0.50 ^c	0.24±0.01 ^a	12.80±0.11 ^a
L1G3	25% PB + 6 mm G	64.59±2.85 ^a	20.31±0.18 ^a	0.25±0.02 ^a	13.57±0.91 ^a
L2G3	50% PB + 6 mm G	66.15±0.91 ^a	19.40±0.49 ^{bc}	0.24±0.00 ^a	12.75±0.43 ^a
L0G0	Control	63.28±0.32 ^a	19.21±0.49 ^c	0.25±0.01 ^a	13.00±0.18 ^a

In a column, means with the same small superscript letters are not significantly different according to Duncan's test at a significance level of 5%. Results showed Mean±SD.

223 In conclusion, 4 mm width girdling of 50% primary branches, reduces alternate bearing
 224 behaviour in 'China' litchi. In our experiment, cumulative yield was increased by 2.07 times with
 225 regard to un-girdled trees during the four years of the trial. The assessment of alternate bearing
 226 through ABI (*I*) is misleading because *I* is sensitive to fluctuation in yield during ON and OFF

227 years and it is not representing the tree's total fruit production in long term. LTYI is more reliable
228 for assessment of alternate bearing along with yield fluctuations under different treatments.

229 **AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTION:**

230 Conceptualization of research (BD, PP and AKS); Designing of experiment (MKD, BD and SG);
231 Field/lab experiments and data collection (MKD and SG); data interpretation (MKD and BD);
232 Preparation of the manuscript (MKD and BD).

233 **DECLARATION**

234 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

235 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENT**

236 Authors are thankful to the Director of ICAR – Research Complex for Eastern Region for
237 providing the requisite field and laboratory facilities. Authors are also like to thank staff members
238 of ICAR - All India Coordinated Research Project for the regular guidance for the trial.

239 This work (Trial number: 4.3.3 L.) was funded by the ICAR - All India Coordinated Research
240 Project on Fruits, India.

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